

WARRIORS OF LIGHT: EXPLORING THE LIVED EXPERIENCES OF POWER LINEMEN AT WORK

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Abstract: The study offers valuable insights for industrial/organizational psychology, electrical engineers, electricians, linemen, Northern Davao Electric Cooperative, Inc. (NORDECO), the Human Resource Department, and government agencies like National Electrification Administration (NEA). It highlights workplace stress, resilience, and peer support, informing strategies to enhance employee well-being, reduce burnout, and improve safety behaviors. From an I/O perspective, the findings contribute to occupational health and safety by emphasizing for mental health support, stress management programs, and a strong safety culture particularly in high-risk environment. Electrical engineers can benefit from improved training, technical skills, and safer infrastructure designs, while electricians and linemen are encouraged to prioritize safety protocols, skills development, and coping mechanisms in high-risk environments. For Northern Davao Electric Cooperative, Inc. (NORDECO), the findings suggest ways to boost employee retention, operational efficiency, and customer service. The Human Resource Department can develop professional programs and support systems tailored to linemen's challenges. Lastly, National Electrification Administration (NEA) and other agencies are encouraged to implement better policies, safety standards, and training programs to strengthen the workforce and improve the performance of electrical cooperatives.

Keywords: Workplace Stress, Safety Behaviors, Employee Retention, Skills Development, Organizational Practices
SDG Indicator: Goal 8 (Decent Work and Economic Growth), Target 8.8 (Protect labor rights and promote safe working environments for all workers).

1. INTRODUCTION

As described, electrical power linemen are the workers who build and maintain power lines from generating plants to homes, factories, and stores. They work on high-voltage transmission lines, substations, distribution lines, and even run wires to consumers' houses. To become a lineman, one must complete basic training, typically consisting of 400 hours over one to two months, and obtain Occupational Safety and Health certification (Miller, 2019). Upon graduation from an apprenticeship program, linemen have the option to either remain at their current workplace or take their skills to other locations to help build power lines. Similarly, Tri-County Electric Cooperative in Texas honors employees who contribute to keeping the lights on (White & Brown, 2020).

Over the years, research impacts on work environment, specifically among linemen workers who has gained significant attention. As highlighted by Noor et al. (2021), linemen were exposed to unique combinations of physical, psychological, and environmental stressors that increase the risk of electrocution and death. Smith et al., 2020 further added, that this surge in research can be attributed to the growing recognition of how high levels of perceived stress can affect workers health and well-being, making stress a public health concern. Linemen's stress, often derived from the hazardous conditions of their job, requires further study to develop interventions that can improve their working environments.

In contrast, a significant research gap remains in understanding the psychosocial aspects of linemen's experiences, primarily how they cope with stress, build resilience, and maintain productivity under hazardous conditions. As such, there is an existing frameworks proposed by Sørensen et al. (2021), such as the Stress Process Model (SPM) where it explores how stressors follow social patterns and culminate in various strains.

The said model indicates that external stressors such as job demands, safety risks, and work environments interact with personal and social resources are affecting an individual's ability to cope with stress. While on the other hand, Andrews & Rourke (2022) emphasize the said model in which stress is a process influenced by both environmental and personal factors, where in it lacks a specific focus on high-risk professions, such as linemen, where extreme working conditions require specialized stress management strategies. Therefore, this gap will underscore the need for a more targeted approach to stress research in high-risk environments.

Global Perspective on Power Linemen's Experiences, Stress and Productivity, which depicts a relationship with each other. According to Bui et al. (2021), relevant associations were found with higher levels of stress related to reduced productivity. However, less research is focused on the areas of intersectionality between stress management, safety adherence, and service quality, especially in community-driven initiatives like NORDECO's Kalinga ng NORDECO Corporate Social Responsibility (CSR) program, as found in Garcia et al. (2023). This study aims to fill this gap by exploring how linemen's stress management strategies influence service quality and consumer satisfaction, especially in electrification projects and its operations that have significant social impact.

This study seeks to add fresh perspectives to the way linemen manage the psychological aspects of the job's stressors, this time looking into how work environments influence their mental health and social functioning. Organizational interventions on reducing stress need to be understood for improving overall well-being and performance among linemen (Wilson et al., 2021). The Martinez and Perez study of 2021 focuses on how faith, resilience, and coping mechanisms interplay to impact the ability of linemen to perform in high-stress, high-risk environments. The results will expand workplace psychology by demonstrating how spiritual beliefs can be leveraged to manage stress and job satisfaction, thus filling a gap in the literature for high-risk professions.

The work environment for linemen poses major challenges related to work-life balance, which exposes them to stressors such as heavy workloads, conflicts with colleagues, job insecurity, and poor working conditions (Kamarulzaman et al., 2017; Yim et al., 2018; Yang et al., 2017; Ren et al., 2018). Badre (2021) further show that occupational stress results from an imbalance between job demands and coping abilities, compounded by limited timeframes, which further complicates their experiences. Even though, it is confronted by all these challenges, Cruz and Roldan (2022) also shows that family support is a determinant of increased work-life balance and better mental health for linemen. However, long working hours, irregular schedules may cause difficulties. Further clarification from Del Rosario & Alcantara, 2019 reveals safety issues such as electrical shock, falls, and other physical injuries are critical risks linemen face.

Moreover, Escobar & Mendoza (2019) also argues that these risks may have long-term physical health consequences; in fact, studies demonstrate a higher risk of cardiovascular diseases, musculoskeletal disorders, and other job-related health problems among linemen stemming from work-related stress. Zhang et al. (2018) discussed the family support role in improving job satisfaction, while research by Basson (2021) and Okechukwu (2022) emphasized that self-esteem, social support, and perceived control favor adaptive coping strategies. Furthermore, faith and resilience as integrated by Bui et al. (2021) expands workplace psychology through the demonstration of how spiritual beliefs enhance stress management and job satisfaction, filling in the gap for understanding the human side of high-risk professions. This study has shown the role of faith as a coping mechanism, emphasizing how spiritual beliefs foster mental resilience among linemen working in hazardous environments.

From the DEC perspective, linemen have challenges that are unique and worthy of extensive study as living experiences. Though some might have been deterred by the valuables acquired through studies on occupational stress that linemen endure (Alvez & Rodrigues, 2021; Escobar & Mendoza, 2019; Ramirez & Ortiz, 2020), much is still unknown about these experiences, especially in the Davao locality. This research addresses the above challenge by conducting qualitative, region-specific studies that offer localized understanding of linemen's challenges and coping mechanisms. Moreover, this study will explore the relationship between psychological well-being of linemen and their job performance. This study advances our knowledge about how well-being impacts job performance (Salgado et al., 2019). This research will also look into the moderating role of perceived job insecurity in the relationship (Ismail et al., 2019). In particular, this research offers the opportunity to fill the knowledge gap and give voice to the linemen of Davao Region by capturing their struggles, coping mechanisms, and resilience. The findings can inform local policies and interventions to improve their mental health, work-life balance, and overall job satisfaction.

Besides this, the research may have a wider impact in terms of maximizing social service projects in the electricity industry, hence improving the lives of linemen and the people they serve.

2. METHOD

This section provide general description of the study participants, materials and instruments, design, and procedure that are vital for making this research substantial, valid, and reliable.

Study Participants

This study used purposive sampling for the recruitment of ten (10) power linemen from Northern Davao Electric Cooperative, Davao de Oro. For in-depth interviews and held one focus group discussion or follow-up interviews with seven linemen. Participants included current linemen with at least three to ten years of service, who would be willing to share their experiences regarding work stress, coping mechanisms, and their social and psychological well-being. Excluded were those not actively serving as linemen, with less than three years of service, or in non-field roles. For in-depth interviews (IDIs), linemen with three to ten years of experience were prioritized to ensure that seasoned professionals could share insights about industry changes, technological advancements, safety protocols, and organizational dynamics. Focus-group discussion (FGDs) included linemen with three or more years of experience, hoping to create a diverse pool of perspectives from both experienced workers and newer entrants. Job roles, work environments, and tenure-specific challenges were also considered as necessary. Participants were rejected if they had retired, been transferred to not-so-field jobs, or refused to communicate their personal experience. Employers in higher management and administration were also rejected to keep the study single-mindedly focused on active linemen who remained in field work. Any participant was allowed to withdraw from the study at any time without reasons or repercussions negatively targeted toward them; hence, ethical considerations were followed by the comfort of the participants during this process (Peng et al., 2023)

Materials and Instruments

This study employed a Key Informant Interview (KII) guide that was further categorized according to the research objectives: occupational stressors, social and family support, and the psychological well-being of DEC power linemen. A systematic questionnaire, which remained undisguised, was utilized as the instrument for data collection. Secondary sources were obtained through published documents and materials available for public use.

The questionnaire has background and personal information sections. Besides, the review integrated a meta-analysis of other studies to study associations between social stressors, occupational stressors, and well-being (Gerhardt et al., 2021). An interview guide is validated by five subject matter experts. The guide attained an average rating of 9, described as good. Hence, the guide used is valid.

Design and Procedure

This research study was endorsed by the Dean of the Graduate Studies Department in the university before commencement of the research. The following three instruments were then deployed after approval: interview guide, field observations, and field notes. An interview guide was prepared for the IDIs and FGDs. The guide included open questions meant to elicit rich responses about the lived experiences of power linemen, how they cope, and how this impact affects their work and personal lives. The questions were grounded in a thorough literature review and the theoretical framework of the study. A pilot test was done to ensure the questions were clear and would provide the needed data (Creswell & Poth, 2018). Field observations were held in aid of interview and FGD data. The researcher observed the work environment, interactions, and daily routines of the power linemen for a well-rounded experience, confirming the self-reported data. Field notes are taken during and immediately after each interview session and observation to observe nonverbal responses, emotional outcomes, environmental context, and the researcher's initial impressions (Pacheco-Vega, 2019). Development of these research instruments was through an iterative process: drafting, review by experts, pilot testing, and revisions for reliability and validity. These were best practices for developing qualitative research instruments (Creswell & Poth, 2018).

The data were transcribed and analyzed via thematic analysis. Given the strict importance of the need for accuracy in this study, the researcher collaborated with a data analyst from the university. Thematic analysis, according to Nowell et al. (2017), is a qualitative method used in identifying, analyzing, and reporting patterns within data. It follows the six-stage procedure: (1) familiarizing with the data, (2) generating preliminary codes, (3) looking for themes, (4) reviewing themes, (5) defining and naming themes, and (6) producing the final report. In terms of trustworthiness, the research adopted Elo et al.'s (2014) recommendations regarding credibility, dependability, confirmability, and transferability. Credibility relates to the genuineness of data, dependability requires peer reviews, and it is ensured that the process is consistent throughout the

research. Confirmability reduces researcher bias, while transferability establishes the ability to transfer findings into other settings. Data verification both at the time of collection and analysis strengthened the reliability and validity of the study.

To ensure confirmability, the researcher reduced personal bias and remained objective in the process (Connelly, 2016). Transferability focuses on the applicability of findings to similar contexts or populations, realizing that generalizability is not the main goal. The ability to demonstrate transferability can be done by providing rich descriptions of the research setting, assumptions, and participant context, allowing other researchers to judge the applicability of the findings to their own contexts (Shenton, 2004).

The UM Ethics Review Committee ethical guidelines were followed by the researcher in ensuring participant safety and well-being throughout the study. The research process was conducted ethically, avoiding exposing participants to risks that were not necessary (Polit & Beck, 2017; Munhall, 2014). Participant autonomy, confidentiality, informed consent, and voluntary participation were adhered to (Beauchamp & Childress, 2019).

Participants were fully aware of the study's objectives, possible risks, and benefits to them. They were assured of their autonomy and the right to participate voluntarily without any consequence to their decisions. The researcher ensured that informed consent was undertaken by all participants before conducting interviews with them and also accounted for the no harm guarantee in terms of not causing any physical or psychological harm before, during, and after the study.

To maintain academic integrity, the researcher restated content without any form of plagiarism, using Turnitin, which is the university's plagiarism detection tool, and Grammarly, to make it clearer and in proper structure for writing. The researcher made sure that nothing was changed and nothing was deleted and no tampering of data. Before making the interviews, permission was received from the Human Resource Department of Northern Davao Electric Cooperative, Inc. in Davao de Oro. All technology-related concerns were addressed, and appropriate citation was given to all sources used in this study.

Throughout the research process, the researcher ensured that copyright laws were respected and is open to publishing the findings, with joint authorship with the co-author and research advisor. All research procedures adhered to the protocols established by the UM Ethics Review Committee, as evidenced by the Certificate of Approval with Protocol No. UMER-2024-142 (Flick, 2018; Kallet, 2021).

3. RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

This section presents the participants' experiences as power linemen, focusing on their challenges, coping strategies, and key insights. It also highlights the various themes and core ideas derived from the in-depth interviews and focus group discussions conducted with the study's participants. Additionally, this section provides an overview of the responses shared by other participants throughout the study.

Table 1: Themes on the lived experiences of linemen in the course of performing their duties

THEMES	CORE IDEAS
Always praying for safety	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • We always ensure safety to avoid accidents. • Safety precautions are always in place and constantly reminded by our safety officers. • It's very dangerous, especially when troubleshooting lines, which is extremely difficult and risky. • We always pray for our safety. • Sometimes, accidents can't be avoided, especially incidents of electrocution.
Experiencing body malaise and pains	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Feeling physical pain in the body, possibly due to past challenges faced in the job • Experiencing over fatigue, especially around 4:00 PM • Even after clocking out, feeling extremely tired but having to return if a line is cut

	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ● Struggling with physical exhaustion from climbing to reconnect broken wires ● The job is exhausting, particularly when dealing with cut lines and difficult internet wires, which drain energy completely
Encountering conflict with coworkers or consumers	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ● Struggling with external threats ● Emphasizing the importance of communication with colleagues for smooth operations ● Handling negative comments from consumers ● Remaining calm despite disrespectful behavior from consumers in the field ● Showing humility despite disrespectful consumers ● Maintaining good communication and advice among teammates

Table 1 presents the themes and core ideas observed from the participants' responses regarding the lived experiences and challenges they encountered. The analysis focused on understanding power linemen's lived experiences and their suggestions for improving service delivery. Three key themes emerged from the interviews:

Always praying for safety, Experiencing body malaise and pains, and Encountering conflict with coworkers or consumers.

Workplace hazards emerged as a central theme. Participants described the dangerous nature of their work, particularly during line clearing and troubleshooting. Jr., a 38-year-old lineman with 14 years of service, expressed feelings of sadness and disheartenment due to the challenges they faced. He and other participants noted inadequate resources, such as insufficient manpower, vehicles, safety measures, and PPE, as major issues. These deficiencies contributed to various incidents, including mild injuries.

Always praying for safety

The first theme emphasized the significant risks involved in being a lineman, particularly during high-risk situations. The level of danger fluctuates depending on the complexity of the tasks and environmental factors such as weather and terrain. Linemen expressed a constant fear of accidents while handling high-voltage lines, which can have serious implications for their safety and well-being.

For instance, Participant 1 (Mon) shared his experience, stating:

Lisod ug delikado ang troubleshooting sa linya, pero kinahanglan kayanon para sa pamilya. Ako, mag-amping sa trabaho, mag-ampo, ug magpokus sa safety sa tanan nga oras. (FGD_P1_Q1).

Troubleshooting the line is difficult and dangerous, but it must be done for the family. I stay cautious in my work, pray, and focus on safety at all times.

Mon highlights personal caution, prayer, and safety focus, aligning with Lombardi et al. (2009) on linemen's risks. However, Hale et al. (2010) argue that structured protocols and training are more crucial for safety than individual vigilance. While Mon sees troubleshooting as unpredictable, Reason (1997) suggests risks can be mitigated through systematic procedures. His reliance on prayer for safety aligns with Pargament (1997) on stress coping, but Clarke (2013) stresses that enforcement of safety protocols is more effective in preventing accidents.

Similarly, Participant 2 (Roy) expressed how his past experiences with electrocution made him realize the importance of safety, reinforcing his routine of praying to avoid accidents:

Ang trabaho isip lineman, lisod, kapoy... tanan na naa, sakit, kapoy, gutom, Niagi ko ug Job Order (JO) sa 2016, na lay-off ko, pagbalik nako sa 2018, gibutang ko sa clearing, ug sa reorganization, gibutang gihapon ko as lineman, Pasalamat ko nga naa ko diri, makatrabaho, makapalit sa gusto. Naka-experience ko nga nakuryentehan ug na-shock, mao nga importante gyud ang safety, ampo pirmi sa Ginoo. Lisod kaayo mawala ang akong mga kauban, mao amping pirmi (21:05_P2_Q1).

Being a lineman is tough and exhausting—pain, fatigue, and hunger. After being laid off in 2016, I returned in 2018 and was reassigned as a lineman. I'm grateful for this job that allows me to work and provide. I've been electrocuted before, so I prioritize safety and always pray. Losing my colleagues would be hard, so I stay cautious.

The practice of praying for safety is common in high-risk professions, with workers seeking divine protection (Ellis & Swenson, 2021). However, this contrasts with studies emphasizing structured safety protocols, training, and PPE. Smith (2020) argues that while prayer provides emotional support, it cannot replace evidence-based safety measures. White et al. (2019) highlight the importance of safety culture and training over individual religious practices, suggesting that relying on prayer may distract from implementing more effective safety practices. Leong et al. (2018) further emphasize that spiritual practices should complement, not replace, safety procedures. Their study shows that combining emotional resilience with proper training and safety protocols is more effective in reducing accidents and ensuring worker safety.

Experiencing body malaise and pains

The second theme dealt with the physical strain and discomfort linemen experience daily. These challenges are far greater compared to those in non-field roles. Linemen endure constant fatigue, physical pain, and the long-term effects of their demanding tasks. Despite this, their dedication to the work and the camaraderie with colleagues keep them motivated.

Participant 3 (Toto) recalled his most unforgettable experience working in the rugged terrain of Mt. Diwata, also known as Diwalwal, in Monkayo, Davao de Oro:

Luha ug singot nag-abot, labi na katong na-assign mi sa Diwalwal. Nagsugod ko diri 2001, nakaagi ko sa kalisod sa Bagyong Pablo ug hangtod karon, naa gihapon sakit sa lawas tungod sa mga kalisod sa trabaho isip lineman. Pero nakamotivate ko tungod sa camaraderie sa mga kauban ug sa mga tawo. Kinahanglan magpabiling humble ug kalma bisan masuko ang uban kay empleyado ra ta. (FGD_P3_Q1).

Tears and sweat mixed, especially when we were assigned to Diwalwal. I started in 2001 and faced hardships during Typhoon Pablo, which still affect me physically. Despite the challenges, I'm dedicated to my work. What motivates me is the camaraderie with my colleagues and the people. I stay composed and avoid confrontation, remembering to remain humble since we're just employees.

Toto highlights camaraderie as a key motivator, aligning with Bakker & Demerouti (2007) on social support enhancing job commitment. However, Schaufeli et al. (2009) argue that intrinsic motivation and job resources, such as training and fair compensation, play a more critical role in long-term engagement. He also stresses humility and composure in dealing with difficult consumers, which aligns with Grandey (2000) on emotional labor. Yet, Hochschild (1983) warns that prolonged emotional regulation can lead to burnout, suggesting that humility alone may not prevent work-related stress. His account of lingering physical strain echoes Punnett et al. (2005) on the long-term health risks of physically demanding jobs, yet Waters & Dick (2015) emphasize that proper ergonomic interventions and work modifications are crucial in mitigating these effects.

Participant 4 (Optimus) also described troubleshooting the line as one of the most difficult aspects of a lineman's duties:

Lisod ug delikado ang troubleshooting sa linya, pero kinahanglan kayanon para sa pamilya. Ako, mag-amping sa trabaho, mag-ampo, ug magpokus sa safety sa tanan nga oras. (FGD_P4_Q1).

Troubleshooting the line is difficult and dangerous, but it must be done for the family. I stay cautious in my work, pray, and focus on safety at all times.

Optimus states that troubleshooting is both difficult and dangerous, which aligns with studies on high-voltage work risks (e.g., Lombardi et al., 2009). However, Reason (1997) suggests that systematic safety measures can reduce these risks. He also emphasizes individual precaution, prayer, and a focus on safety. Yet, Hale et al. (2010) argue that personal measures are less effective without comprehensive safety protocols, and Clarke (2013) notes that prayer and personal coping do not replace formal safety procedures.

Encountering conflict with coworkers or consumers

The third theme concerned conflicts with coworkers or consumers, which often arise in high-pressure fieldwork. Effective communication with colleagues is essential for smooth operations, while maintaining professionalism helps in dealing with difficult consumers. Linemen frequently encounter negative comments from consumers but try to stay calm and humble despite disrespectful behavior. Professionalism and good communication within the team are crucial for managing these challenges.

Participant 5 (Jr.) shared his experience of handling difficult consumers during critical moments in the field:

Usahay naay consumer magpasurang-surang sa field, pero usahay paubos lang gyud ta, utong lang gyud. Kay nanarbaho man ta diri, sila man atong boss, mao serbosityong kinasingkasing ra jud. (16:00_FGD_Q2.2B)

Sometimes there are consumers who are difficult to deal with in the field, but we just have to remain patient. Because we work here, they are our bosses, so it's really a heartfelt service.

Jr. emphasizes that remaining patient is key when dealing with challenging consumers. While this approach aligns with research on emotional labor (e.g., Grandey, 2000), studies such as those by Morgeson and Humphrey (2008) suggest that relying solely on individual patience can lead to increased stress and emotional exhaustion if not supported by formal conflict-resolution strategies and organizational resources. Jr. states that consumers are treated as "bosses," implying that heartfelt service is essential.

However, research by Bitner (1990) indicates that such power dynamics can result in heightened consumer ice is important, balancing this with employee well-being is crucial for sustainable service quality.

Participant 6 (Kiford) also shared his approach to managing consumer complaints in the field: expectations and potential employee strain. Further, Zeithaml et al. (1996) argue that while customer serv

Magstoryag di maayo ang mga konsumante, pero makaya raman paubos lang gyud (23:02_FGD_Q2.2A)

Consumers may complain, but we can handle it with patience.

Kiford emphasizes that consumer complaints can be managed with patience. While this aligns with research on emotional labor (e.g., Grandey, 2000), studies such as Morgeson and Humphrey (2008) argue that relying solely on individual patience may lead to emotional exhaustion if not supported by formal conflict-resolution mechanisms. He suggests that personal resilience is sufficient to handle complaints. However, research by Bitner (1990) and Zeithaml et al. (1996) indicates that structured, organizational support is also necessary to effectively manage consumer dissatisfaction and mitigate employee strain

Table 2: Themes on the Coping Mechanism of Power Linemen

THEMES	CORE IDEAS
Promoting healthy working environment	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Practicing patience with coworkers, understanding the potential for frustration but striving to stay calm to prevent conflicts • Valuing communication and offering advice to ensure smooth operations in the field • Recognizing the importance of support from colleagues, as they are often daily partners, fostering strong bonds • Feeling supported by coworkers, especially when help is needed to complete tasks • Appreciating the teamwork and assistance provided by colleagues during challenging moments on the job
Being understanding and kind to everyone	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Encountering aggressive consumers who may seem to know more about the job, presenting a challenge but managing to stay calm • Choosing not to engage with shouting or complaining consumers • Understanding and patiently dealing with consumers who are upset • Collaborating with coworkers to maintain good relationships despite the exhaustion, as it is better to keep things amicable

Table 2 presents the themes and core ideas observed from the participants' responses when asked about the coping mechanisms they use in dealing with the challenges they face in their line of work. The analysis aimed to understand the strategies employed by power linemen to maintain well-being and ensure effective service delivery. Their responses revealed two (2) key themes: *Promoting a healthy working environment and being understanding and kind to everyone.*

Promoting healthy working environment

Promoting a healthy working environment was highlighted as a key coping mechanism for power linemen. Despite the challenges and risks of the job, having supportive and cooperative colleagues helps linemen manage stress and exhaustion. Participants emphasized the importance of positive relationships with teammates, as this camaraderie offers both emotional support and practical assistance in the field.

Participant 7 (Blacky) emphasized that maintaining a healthy work environment is crucial for coping with the challenges of being a lineman. He highlighted that having a supportive team where everyone communicates and works together makes the job less stressful and more manageable:

Balik-balikon gyud nako na maayo gyud permi ang feedbacking kay tungod makapromote man gud ni ug maayo nga komunikasyon sa akong kaubanan ug mga tao isip pod kauban sa buhat nga Foreman, na luyo sa kakapoy ug daghan problema sa field dapat maintain lang gyud ang maayo nga relasyon sa matag-usa, positive lang gyud permi aron mapadali ang trabaho sa matag adlaw (15:006_P7_Q3.1.3)

I'll always emphasize the importance of feedback because it promotes good communication among my colleagues and the people, including the Foreman. Despite fatigue and numerous field problems, maintaining a good relationship with each other is crucial. Staying positive always helps ease the daily workload.

However, some research findings challenge this perspective. For instance, a study by Bakker et al. (2007) on job demands and resources found that while social support can buffer stress, it is insufficient in highly hazardous environments where external pressures outweigh internal support systems. Similarly, Hobfoll's (1989) COR theory stipulates that most of the reduction in workplace stress arises from resource gain, such as better safety measures and reduced workload, rather than relying solely on social relationships. These findings indicate that while camaraderie helps, it may not have a total effect of mitigating occupational stress in high-risk jobs such as power linemen.

Participant 8: Tetus Participant 8 is Tetus, who believes that the key to fulfilling the mission as a lineman is to genuinely love the work. He emphasized that viewing the job not merely as a task but as a calling helps maintain motivation and commitment, especially during challenging moments in the field:

Sa akong mga kaubanan nga lineman, dapat manarabaho gyud ug tinud-anay,kay kasagaran naa koy amigo, sigeg lipay-lipay nakalimtan na ang pamilya, walay tigum, pag-uli gubot na focus.. ah. Be responsible gyud ta. Kay ug wala na focus lang ta sa lingaw-lingaw, wala gyud ta. (00:04_P8_Q3.1.3)

For my fellow linemen, we should work diligently and responsibly because most of us have families. If we keep on enjoying ourselves and forget about our responsibilities, there won't be any progress. It's important to be responsible because if we just focus on having fun, we won't achieve anything.

Contrary to this, research by Maslach and Leiter (2016) on burnout indicates that passion alone does not protect workers from exhaustion. Their study found that excessive job involvement without adequate recovery time leads to burnout, particularly in high-risk professions. This contradicts the notion that passion alone can sustain motivation, suggesting that structural interventions, such as regulated rest periods and job redesign, may be more effective in maintaining well-being.

Being understanding and kind to everyone

Being kind to everyone is another key coping mechanism for power linemen. Despite the job's challenges, maintaining a compassionate attitude toward coworkers, consumers, and the public fosters cooperation and eases tense situations. Participants emphasized that kindness contributes to smoother operations and a harmonious work environment, reducing stress and strengthening teamwork.

Participant 9 (Roy) highlighted the importance of understanding and kindness in every aspect of a lineman's job:

Kaubanan gyud sa field ang makatabang permi kay kamo man permi mag-atubang pag naa sa field, magkasinabot ragyud mo dinha, communication sa imong kauban ug maayo nga relasyon. (30:02_P9_Q2.3B)

The camaraderie among colleagues in the field is always beneficial because you frequently encounter challenges while working there. You have a mutual understanding, effective communication with your colleagues, and maintain positive relationships

However, research by Grandey et al. (2012) on emotional labor suggests that while kindness can enhance workplace interactions, it can also contribute to emotional exhaustion, particularly in customer-facing roles. Their study indicates that continuously managing emotions to maintain harmony, particularly in hostile situations, can lead to stress accumulation rather than stress relief. This suggests that while kindness is beneficial, relying solely on it without addressing external stressors may not be a sustainable coping mechanism.

Participant 10 (John) highlighted the importance of understanding and kindness in the lineman role. He emphasized that being compassionate towards coworkers and consumers promotes better communication, reduces conflicts, and ensures smoother operations, especially during challenging situations:

Akong mga kauban, suportado gyud ko sa pagpanarbaho, kay usahay mangutana man ko og unsay maayo ani labi na sa paghandle sa mga konsumante na perti ka init ug ulo sa field diritso dayun banghag ba magtinabangay gyud mis akong kauban, open gyud mi, kay kung ako lang mag desisyon dili man pod, sharing of ideas lang. Para unsay dali, kung makita nako nga mas dali ilaha, go ana lang.. (21:47_P10_Q2.3B)

My colleagues really support me in my work, especially when I ask for advice on how to handle difficult consumers who are very hot-headed in the field. We immediately work together and help each other. We're open with each other because if I were to make the decision alone, it wouldn't work. It's all about sharing ideas to find the quickest solution, and if I see that their approach is easier, then I go with it.

In contrast, research by Zapf and Holz (2006) on occupational stress suggests that while collaboration enhances problem-solving, it does not always guarantee reduced stress levels. Their findings indicate that in high-pressure environments, decision-making under stress can lead to cognitive overload, where workers struggle to make optimal choices despite teamwork. This contrasts with the participant's belief that sharing ideas inherently leads to better solutions, highlighting the need for structured problem-solving frameworks to enhance efficiency.

Table 3: Themes on insights shared by participants to improve the service delivery performance of power linemen.

THEMES	CORE IDEAS
Management must provide trainings	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Management approaches to up skilling linemen vary, and not everyone has the opportunity due to budget constraints. • Training has become simpler compared to the past. • There is a need for refresher training to improve the work of linemen, as their tasks are routine. • Training is not held regularly, and those who haven't attended are often the ones selected for the next sessions. • More frequent training would greatly benefit the public.
Improvement in Equipment and other Logistical needs	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • A major issue is the vehicle; we only have one vehicle for the team. • We lack equipment, which sometimes leads to injuries because the safety gear we use is likely of lower quality. • Management should focus on addressing these shortages to ensure better safety and efficiency.
Promote Good Communication among co-workers and consumers	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Proper communication among everyone is essential, as it leads to finding solutions to issues. • Always emphasize the importance of feedback because it promotes good communication. • We need regular feedback, as we can't always know what has been accomplished or left undone by others when someone takes over. • How you treat your colleagues' matters; respect is crucial in maintaining good relationships.

Table 3 presents the different themes and core ideas derived from the participants' insights on improving the service delivery performance of power linemen. The three (3) themes that can enhance both operational efficiency and safety in their work are: *Management must provide trainings, Improvement in Equipment and other Logistical needs, Promote Good Communication among co-workers and consumers.*

Management must provide trainings:

Several studies have emphasized the significance of training in improving workforce efficiency and safety in technical fields. The findings in this study highlight that linemen face limited training opportunities due to budget constraints, leading to disparities in up skilling.

Participant 7 (Blacky) shared that the past training sessions were intense and challenging. While tough, he emphasized that they were essential for preparing linemen to handle the complex and risky nature of the job. The training, though difficult, played a key role in enhancing their skills and confidence in the field.

Kuyaw ang training sa una kay mano-mano gyud, i-measure gyud imong skills ug maayo sama anang pila ramo ka lineman tudloan mo unsaon pagdiskarte namakapatindog ug makakaya mog alsa anang poste o unsa pa nga bug-at nga mga equipments sa field na kamo kamo ra, di jud basta basta labi nag gamay ray equipment kay tungod pod sa kuwang sa budget ang management (20:30_P7_Q3).

Training back then was really tough and hands-on. Your skills were thoroughly tested, with only a few linemen being taught how to manage to set up and lift poles or heavy equipment in the field, relying solely on each other. It was no easy task, especially with limited equipment due to budget constraints from management.

This finding contrasts with Li and Zhang (2020), who found that modern linemen training now integrates simulations, augmented reality, and automated assessments, improving safety and efficiency. Unlike Participant 7's experience of manual, resource-limited training, structured programs with technological support significantly reduce workplace injuries (Gao et al., 2019). While hands-on training is valuable, research suggests that supplementing it with technology enhances overall preparedness (Williams et al., 2022).

Participant 3 (Toto) expressed concerns about the lack of fairness in up skilling opportunities for linemen, mentioning that not everyone gets included in the training sessions. He highlighted that this uneven access to training limits the potential for some linemen to improve their skills and further contribute to the team's performance:

Lahi-Lahi man gud ang pamaagi sa management sa pag upskill sa amo isip lineman, dili tanan ba maka apil kay tungod lagi nagbudget ba, dili parehas sa uban Electric Coop ba na, bag-o na ilang equipments naa nay skada tas ilang ginapang gamit sa address sa complaints high-tech na. Tungod suportado sa management sa Coop nila. Kita man gud diri karaan pa na pamaagi ug dili tawagan sa konsumante na naay problema sa linya sa mga hilit na lugar, dili pod ma aksyonan, kay kulang sa tao ug walay equipment na mu-detek automatic ba sama anang skada. (17:00_P3_Q3)

The management's approach to upskilling us as linemen varies. Not everyone can participate because of budget constraints. Unlike other Electric Coops that have new equipment and use high-tech solutions like SCADA to address complaints, our methods are still outdated. Their management fully supports them, while here, the old ways persist. If consumers from remote areas don't call about a line issue, it won't be addressed due to a lack of personnel and no equipment like SCADA to automatically detect problems.

This perspective contrasts with McBride et al. (2018), who found that equitable training improves workforce efficiency and service reliability. Unlike Participant 3's experience, research shows that continuous learning boosts retention and competency (Ramirez & Chen, 2020). Davies and Harper (2021) also found that SCADA integration reduces response times, highlighting a gap in infrastructure investment that could enhance service reliability despite budget constraints.

Improvement in Equipment and other Logistical needs

This was highlighted as crucial for enhancing service delivery. Participants stressed the need for better tools, vehicles, and safety gear to increase efficiency and reduce risks. Adequate equipment would allow linemen to work more effectively and safely, minimizing delays and accidents. Access to timely logistical support would ensure smoother operations and quicker responses to urgent situations.

Participant 5 (Jr.) raised concerns about delays due to insufficient vehicles and supervision, stressing the need for better leadership, teamwork, and resource allocation:

Dugay nagyud namong mulo, nga sa amo nga mga linemen gud, among problema sa vehicle gyud, dapat gyud sa amoa, isa raman gud among sakyanan, gamiton sya ug 8AM-5PM, pag-uli gamiton napod sa 5PM-12:00 PM. So naay panahon nga daghan ug complaints dili ma kuan.. makuha sa 8AM-5:00PM, kung naa lay is aka vehicle pag in namo alas kwatro, pwede na mugawas dili na maghulat. (19:33_P5_Q3.1.3)

We have long complained about the issue of vehicles for us linemen. We only have one vehicle that we use from 8 AM to 5 PM, and then it's used again from 5 PM to 12 AM. So, there are times when many complaints cannot be addressed from 8 AM to 5 PM. If we only had an extra vehicle, we could attend to the issues as early as 4 PM without having to wait.

This finding contrasts with Carter and Wilson (2019), who emphasize that efficient fleet management reduces service delays and improves consumer satisfaction. Unlike Participant 5's concern about vehicle shortages, well-managed utilities optimize scheduling and expand fleets for faster response times (Lee & Roberts, 2020). Additionally, Mitchell et al. (2021) highlight that strong leadership and proactive planning prevent logistical inefficiencies. The ongoing vehicle shortage suggests a gap in resource planning, contradicting research on data-driven workforce mobility optimization (Henderson & Park, 2022).

Participant 1 (Mon) shared the challenges of working in Boringot, Pantukan, Davao de Oro, highlighting the difficult terrain, harsh weather, and remote location. He emphasized that the job requires both physical endurance and technical skill to ensure safety and efficiency in such demanding conditions:

Sama sa ilaha no, ah... kanang.. ang Boringot sa Pantukan, daku man gud na dihaa nga area pero pito(7) ka sapa pa ang latason labi nag kailangan ilisdan o mag-upgrade ug linya, mutabok pagyud ug sapa usahay masamad pa kay usahay taga hawak man ang tubig, parehas anang ginapost ninyo sa atong page sa NORDECO, ingana kalisod gyud kay labi nag gabie mawal-an ug kuryente mapa ugmaan pa gyud kay lisod man kaayo ug gabie ang dalan, pero pasalamat pod mi sa uban konsumante makasabit kay amo pod ginatan-aw ang kaayuhan sa among kaubanan ug sa among sarili (21:00_P1_Q2.3A)

Just like them, Boringot in Pantukan is a large area with seven streams to cross, especially when there's a need to relocate or upgrade lines. Crossing streams can sometimes be risky, especially when the water is high. This is reflected in the posts on our NORDECO page; it's really challenging, especially at night when there's a power outage until the next day because the roads are very difficult at night.

However, we're grateful to other consumers for understanding because we also prioritize the well-being of our colleagues and ourselves. This finding contrasts with the study of Thompson and Garcia (2020), which highlights that modern utilities implement infrastructure improvements, such as weather-resistant poles and remote monitoring systems, to mitigate challenges in difficult terrains. Unlike Participant 1's experience of navigating harsh conditions with limited resources, research suggests that strategic investments in resilient infrastructure reduce delays and enhance safety (Evans & Miller, 2021).

Additionally, Watson et al. (2022) found that utilities utilizing predictive maintenance and Geographic Information System (GIS) mapping improve efficiency in remote areas, contrary to the reliance on manual assessments described by Participant 1. The challenges faced in Boringot suggest a gap in infrastructure adaptation, differing from best practices in terrain-based risk management (Johnson & Patel, 2023).

Promote Good Communication among co-workers and consumers

Promoting good communication among co-workers and consumers is crucial for improving service delivery. Participants emphasized that clear communication fosters teamwork, ensures efficiency, and helps manage consumer expectations. Regular feedback and discussions between colleagues enhance problem-solving, minimize disruptions, and prioritize safety in the field.

Participant 10 (John) emphasized that effective communication is crucial for linemen, ensuring smooth operations and safety. He highlighted how clear communication with teammates and consumers helps manage tasks and resolve issues, leading to better service and customer satisfaction:

Balik-balikon gyud nako na maayo gyud permi ang feedbacking kay tungod makapromote man gud ni ug maayo nga komunikasyon sa akong kaubanan ug mga tao isip pod kauban sa buhat nga Foreman, na luyo sa kakapoy ug daghan problema sa field dapat maintain lang gyud ang maayo nga relasyon sa matag-usa, positive lang gyud permi aron mapadali ang trabaho sa matag adlaw (15:006_P10_Q3.1.3)

I'll always emphasize the importance of feedback because it promotes good communication among my colleagues and the people, including the Foreman. Despite fatigue and numerous field problems, maintaining a good relationship with each other is crucial. Staying positive always helps ease the daily workload

John emphasizes feedback as key to communication, but research by Argyle (1994) and Hargie (2011) suggests that clarity, active listening, and non-verbal cues are also essential. Therefore, feedback alone may not be enough. While John highlights positive relationships despite fatigue, studies by Baker et al. (2006) and Tepper (2007) show that stress can impair communication and safety, challenging this view.

Additionally, Staw (1997) argues that focusing too much on positivity may neglect problem-solving, making it less effective in the long term.

Participant 5 (Jr.) emphasized that effective communication is crucial for linemen, ensuring smooth operations and safety. He highlighted how clear communication with teammates and consumers helps manage tasks and resolve issues, leading to better service and customer satisfaction:

Ulan ug init no.. ah among gisagubang, sama pa sa sundalo lisod among trabaho kesa nila kaya ng ilaha, makita nilang kalaban kami dili, dili pod matagna gyud ang disgrasya kay kuryente man among kalaban ug ang panahon. Pero bisan paman luyo sa hagit, naa gyud permi ang safety precautions no na permi ginapahinumdom sa atong safety officers, Dapat prepared ta permi before musaka sa poste before mu address sa mga complaints tanawon gyud permi u gang wire sa taas sa poste live ba o dili, unya communication gyud na permi na tarong sa kauban aron ah.. han-ay o, tama soft lang ang dagan sa operasyon sa field ba.. (20:01_P5_Q2).

Rain and heat, ah, are what we face, just like soldiers. Our job is harder than theirs because they can see their enemies, but we can't predict accidents because electricity and the weather are our enemies. But despite the challenge, safety precautions are always there, reminded by our safety officers. We should always be prepared before climbing poles and addressing complaints, always checking if the wires on top of the pole are live or not, and maintaining proper communication with our colleagues for smooth operations in the field.

The participant emphasizes communication for safety, aligned with Hargie (2011), however Schlaepfer et al. (2017) note that stress and fatigue can impair communication. Jr. compares linemen's work to soldiers', but Ploeg et al. (2017) highlight soldiers also face unpredictable dangers, including mental stress, making their work equally dangerous. While Jr. stresses safety precautions, Zohar (2002) supports this, but Clarke (2013) points out that accidents can still occur due to human error or limited resources, suggesting safety measures alone aren't foolproof.

4. DISCUSSION

The findings were examined thoroughly with supporting literature, explaining the challenges, coping strategies, and insights of power linemen. Like other frontline workers, they also face hazardous conditions, physical strain, and consumer conflicts. Through their teamwork, communication, and training, linemen enhance service delivery and safety, ensuring efficient and reliable power services even in tough situations.

This study highlights its camaraderie, perseverance, and dedication of linemen, particularly those in the Northern Davao Electric Cooperative in Davao de Oro. While previous research addresses occupational stress, there is limited understanding of their unique lived experiences in this region. By capturing linemen's narratives, this research uncovers their challenges, coping strategies, and resilience, offering valuable insights.

Using a Hermeneutic Phenomenological Design and narrative inquiry, the study explores the meanings linemen attribute to their experiences, providing a deeper understanding of their work and lives. The findings aim to inform policies and initiatives that support the well-being, job satisfaction, and welfare of power linemen, contributing both to academic knowledge and tangible improvements in their quality of life.

Relevant Experiences of Power linemen in the course of performing their duties

Based on the results, there are three main (3) themes that were drawn from the experiences of Power Linemen in the course of performing their duties. These themes were all drawn from core ideas based on the cut down statements of the participants. These are the following: Always praying for safety, Experiencing body malaise and pains, Encountering conflict with coworkers or consumers.

The work of power linemen is highly demanding both physically and mentally and often emotionally draining. Linemen daily pray for safe service, indicating a reliance on spiritual grounding as a coping mechanism in high-risk professions. Research from the past few decades has underscored faith as enhancing resilience among workers who are subjected to hazardous conditions. For example, Calhoun and Tedeschi (2021) comment that spirituality and prayer provide psychological security in risky occupations. This is according to the paper of Singh et al. (2022), which explains how prayer keeps people calm and focused to work under extreme pressure. This is similar to Albert Bandura's social cognitive theory, especially the self-efficacy, in that belief in one's abilities fosters resilience. For linemen, faith, support systems, and motivation enable them to overcome challenges, demonstrating how cognitive and emotional coping strategies play a crucial role in their well-being and job performance.

Experiencing bodily malaise and physical pain also forms an indispensable part of the daily work a lineman has to do. Such exposure to harsh weather, lifting heavy weights, and repetitive activity leads to problems in the musculoskeletal framework, which in recent studies are increasingly reported. According to Ramos et al. (2023), physically exerting jobs, such as the linemen have, often leave them with chronic fatigue and result in long-term health issues, if not mitigated through the proper use of preventive measures and ergonomic interventions. These physical stresses are further complicated by the psychological and emotional strain that comes from resolving conflicts. Lazarus and Folkman's model (1984) provides this context whereby linemen apply problem-focused as well as emotion-focused coping. The former can take the form of ergonomic intervention or preventive measure while the latter includes building up resilience and social support from coworkers or family members. This conceptualization highlights that providing linemen with resources and interventions will not only reduce their physical strain but will also generally make them healthier. This perspective underscores that enabling linemen is not merely about physical intervention but also developing a support setting where their psychological and emotional welfare is of top priority. Highlighting their pain and giving them tools to get through it will show how it is imperative for the workplace to care about well-being as much as it demands productivity. The problems that linemen face, such as conflicts with coworkers and consumers, were further added. Workplace conflicts that mostly arise from miscommunication, misunderstandings, or differing expectations. In customer-facing roles, such as that of linemen, the pressure to resolve complaints while managing consumers' frustration can lead to emotional exhaustion. According to Johnson et al. (2022), research has shown that workplace conflicts, if unresolved, significantly contribute to burnout and job dissatisfaction. Notably, by using Job Demands-Resources (JD-R) Model (Demerouti et al., 2001), conflicts with coworkers and consumers can be viewed as social demands that increase job strain and reduce overall well-being. When linemen face such interpersonal challenges, their emotional and mental resources are depleted, impacting their performance. A proper work environment should be encouraged through adequate support mechanisms, including effective conflict resolution trainings and means of open communication, to harmonize these challenges and strengthen them in resilience as well as boost their job satisfaction.

Hence, consumer conflicts, especially in case of emergencies or power cuts, can become very stressful, which calls for effective communication and conflict-resolution training.

Coping Strategies used to face Challenges Experience by Power Linemen of Davao Electric Cooperative

Healthy working environment and promotion of understanding and kindness should be vital approaches in overcoming the difficulties facing power linemen. Such measures align with COR Theory (Hobfoll, 1989), whereby individuals should work towards the conservation and creation of resources in efforts to handle stress effectively. Healthy working environments support the provision of physical and psychological resources to power linemen by way of, for instance, ergonomic tools and safety measures; hence reducing the level of burnout and developing resilience (Smith et al., 2022). Similarly, kindness and empathy promote social support, which is an essential resource for the reduction of stress at work (Gonzalez-Mulé et al., 2021). Research in recent times points out the positive effects of such strategies. For example, "a supportive work environment reduces the stress in the workplace and prevents resource depletion. It improves the employee's performance and well-being." Zhang et al. (2022). Moreover, it creates a culture of kindness and mutual respect,

leading to better social cohesion, as proved in Miller and Brown's (2022) study, which stated that empathetic communication at the stressful workplaces reduces conflicts at the workplace and promotes resilience. This underscores the critical need for both systemic and interpersonal strategies in reducing stress and enhancing service delivery. Policies that focus on health and safety, coupled with empathy and understanding, will allow linemen to manage workplace challenges while ensuring their well-being. Such a balanced approach addresses immediate stressors but also promotes sustained resilience and job satisfaction over time. Significant insights can the participants share to help improve the service delivering performance of power linemen

Several factors are required to improve the power linemen's service delivery performance. First, management should continually train the linemen to update their skills and knowledge. Continuous training is a key requirement in adapting to new technologies and safety procedures in risky jobs, as highlighted by Hernandez et al. (2023). This training will also build confidence and competence for the linemen, thus enhancing operational efficiency and safety directly. Improving equipment and logistical needs also is important. Without the proper tools and equipment, performance is affected and so is safety. For example, Ramos et al. (2023) mention how poor equipment causes delays in operations and contributes to the high risk of injuries. Better equipment and technology enhance the smooth running of operations but also reduce physical strain on the linemen to ensure their better long-term welfare. Finally, good inter-personal and internal communication among co-workers and between consumers is important for effective service provision. Clear communication enhances team working, minimizes errors, and increases customer satisfaction. Singh et al. (2023) established that effective communication between the lineman and the customer will ensure the fast settlement of the problem and results in a smooth working environment. The linemen can offer safer and more effective services by opening channels both between the teams and the public.

Moreover, Integrating these insights training, equipment improvement, and communication plays a significant role in the fact that power linemen perform their duties efficiently, safely, and with higher job satisfaction.

Training for linemen develops the needed capabilities to manage increasingly complex and evolving issues at the workplace. Continued professional development informs them on issues of safety measures, new technical knowledge, and ways of solving problems; it minimizes mistakes and ensures fast response during emergency situations. According to Hernandez et al. (2023), continuous training of linemen keeps them versatile in a dangerous work environment and makes them both competent and confident.

Improvements in equipment are also essential. Proper, updated tools and machinery help linemen complete tasks efficiently and reduce the risk of injury. The physical strain that comes with handling outdated or inadequate equipment can lead to long-term health complications, as reported by Ramos et al. (2023). With an investment in better resources and technology, the quality of work is enhanced, but also the overall health and safety of linemen are protected for a better job satisfaction in the long run.

Communication is the backbone of teamwork and customer service. Clear communication among linemen, colleagues, and consumers ensures that tasks are executed smoothly and that safety measures are properly observed. Strong communication has been shown to reduce misunderstandings and errors, thereby fostering a collaborative work environment (Singh et al., 2023). The ability of linemen to communicate effectively with each other and consumers increases the chances of solving problems quickly and maintaining a good relationship with the community they serve. All these elements together make for a holistic approach to improving performance. Training, equipment upgrades, and communication are all important factors that prepare power linemen to meet the demands of their job, thereby improving operational efficiency, safety, and job satisfaction.

IMPLICATIONS AND CONCLUDING REMARKS

Such key implications in the study arise from this to benefit Human Resource Departments, Electricians, Electrical Engineers, Linemen, National Electrification Administration (NEA), Government Agencies, and even the field of Industrial/Organizational Psychology. It guides ways for training and safety, especially on aspects concerning resilience and team cohesion. For HR, better policies are available to promote better well-being, while for linemen and engineers, the same could result from ergonomic tools and better coping mechanisms. These findings can be used by industrial/organizational psychologists to fine-tune workplace interventions and develop healthy work environments. NEA and government departments can influence policy-making processes aimed at working conditions and safety, leading eventually to better efficiency and job satisfaction.

Implications for Practice

The findings of the present study hold great implications for the practical application to human resources, industrial/organizational psychology, and the wider electric utility industry. Power linemen's lived experiences can help different stakeholders make strategic decisions in further improving working conditions, safety standards, and job satisfaction. A finding for HRDs is that integration of such study findings in the curriculum of training and development programs, not only on technical skills but also in connection with emotional resilience, could be accomplished. Continuous professional development and increased accessibility to such training may ensure power linemen are prepared to meet the physiological and psycho-emotional demands of their job. HR policies should also have mental and physical health initiatives to encourage regular check-ins and the provision of resources to prevent burnout and stress.

Industrial/Organizational psychologists can play a key role in understanding how linemen cope with job-related stress and develop strategies to build resilience. By applying theories like the Conservation of Resources (COR) Theory, psychologists can design interventions that focus on resource management, such as training on stress management, conflict resolution, and team-building exercises. Furthermore, they can contribute to creating work environments that foster camaraderie, teamwork, and emotional well-being, which are essential for high-risk occupations like power linemen. For linemen and electrical engineers, this research focuses on enhancing workplace ergonomics and making sure that the safety procedures are followed stringently. Using ergonomic tools and safety measures in the daily routines would greatly reduce physical strain and long-term health problems. In addition, linemen can learn more effective coping mechanisms, such as mindfulness or peer support networks, to manage the emotional stress attached to their job. For NEA and the government, this study would mean that policies to be implemented in favor of linemen about their problem need to be devised, such as providing funds for equipment upgrading and ensuring the proper implementation of safety regulations. Inclusive and fair distribution efforts for resources - including trainings and equipment - will be added aspects to improve the general efficiency and well-being of linemen. Also, governmental agencies would be able to support programs toward the betterment of working conditions for linemen, where safety and emotional wellbeing are considered side by side. In general, these results call for cooperation from HR, industrial/organizational psychologists, management, and governmental agencies in terms of creating work environments that fulfill the technical aspects of the task but also respect the mental and emotional needs of linemen. Such strategies of fostering resilience, improving communication, and better physical conditions would result in the service delivery improving in addition to an increase in job satisfaction and eventually a more efficient and sustainable workforce in the electric utility industry.

Implication for Future Research

This study serves as a basis for further exploration of the lived experiences of linemen, with emphasis on their sense of camaraderie, motivation, and strong faith in God. Future research can expand on these findings by investigating additional factors that influence the well-being and performance of linemen, such as mental health support, professional development opportunities, and the impact of technological advancements in the field. More comparative studies could be conducted across regions or countries regarding the diverse challenges and practices in electric cooperative sectors. It would thus be possible to determine the best practices and strategies that can be adapted globally to improve the effectiveness and safety of the work of linemen. The second area that requires further research is the influence of data-driven decision-making on the operations of linemen. Understanding how new tools and analytics can enhance their daily tasks, safety protocols, and job satisfaction can provide recommendations for cooperatives on how to integrate technology better. This implies, in other words, that cognitive appraisal and adaptive coping strategies are critical to ensuring operational efficiency, safety, and high-quality service delivery by linemen. More importantly, it points out that, by knowing how linemen perceive and respond to stressors, a company like NORDECO can develop specific interventions to support their workforce. This would be accompanied by ongoing training in problem-solving ability as well as creation of a supporting work environment; the psychological needs of linemen have been recognized through promotion of mental well-being in programs. In conclusion, Lazarus and Folkman's Transactional Model of Stress and Coping offers a comprehensive framework to understand the stress and coping processes among linemen. By integrating these concepts into research and practice, we can better support linemen in managing the demands of their profession, ultimately enhancing their performance and overall well-being. Furthermore, this study has its limitations. First, the research is primarily based on qualitative data from a specific electric cooperative, which may not be generalizable to all cooperatives or regions. The purposive sampling method, while effective for in-depth understanding, may also introduce bias as it relies on a selected group of participants who are willing to share their experiences. Additionally, the focus on themes such as camaraderie, motivation, and faith might overlook other significant factors influencing linemen's experiences, such as economic conditions, labor policies, and community relations. Future studies should consider a broader range of variables to provide a more comprehensive understanding. Finally, the

study's reliance on self-reported data can introduce subjective bias, as participants may present their experiences in a more favorable light. Incorporating quantitative data and objective measures in future research could help validate and strengthen the findings. By addressing these limitations and exploring new avenues, future research can continue to build on the knowledge gained from this study, ultimately contributing to the well-being and effectiveness of linemen in the electric cooperative sector.

Concluding Remarks

The overall implication of this study is to indicate the factors critical to power linemen's well-being and performance, where improvements in training, equipment, and communication can help integrate such findings into practice for the creation of a safer and more supportive work environment. Stakeholders from the Human Resource Department, industrial/organizational psychologists, and government agencies would help create this better work environment. Prioritizing both physical and mental health, along with fostering teamwork and resilience, will improve service delivery while boosting job satisfaction, ensuring a more effective and sustainable workforce in the electric utility sector.

Always pray for safety: This leads to resilience; hence, there is incorporation of faith-based coping mechanisms into work practices, and linemen understand that prayer for safety is an important mechanism in managing stress and fostering wellbeing, thereby improving the psychological health and performance of individuals in risky situations.

Physical malaise and body pains; Creating a work environment that promotes the welfare of the linemen-It is important to address the physical demand of the job because, with proper ergonomics training and better access to medical care, linemen can more effectively manage their bodily pain and attenuate the negative impact this has on job satisfaction and productivity.

Increasing conflict with colleagues and customers: Instilling a culture of understanding, constructive conflict resolution, and promoting positive communication can help reduce workplace conflict. Positive interpersonal relations enhance the level of job satisfaction, reduce stress at work, and generally assist in delivering quality services.

Promoting a healthy environment: The work environment must be healthy enough to promote the mental and physical well-being of linemen. Stress management programs, a friendly team culture, and access to wellness resources are all factors that will contribute to the overall health and performance of linemen.

Being considerate and nice to everyone: A culture of kindness and consideration, both within and outside of the organization. Co-workers and in consumer interactions, can significantly enhance workplace morale. A supportive and understanding work environment reduces stress, improves cooperation, and leads to higher job satisfaction and improved service delivery

Management should hold trainings: Management must stress continuous training addressing technical skills, as well as stress management skills. These enable linemen to better cope with challenges, create safety, and ensure that these individuals are far better equipped in handling the rigors of work.

Improvement and equipment and other logistical needs: these include the logistical needs; these have to be provided with modern equipment and resources, so that the linemen will have the means to do their job safely and effectively. Proper equipment reduces safety risks and improves job performance results in higher job satisfaction and quality service delivery.

Promote good communication between co-workers and consumers: Communication is essential for minimizing misunderstandings and fostering teamwork. Both the linemen and consumers will learn better ways to communicate, and this can enhance smooth operations with happy customers.

The findings of the study are consistent with and support the applicability of Lazarus and Folkman's Transactional Model of Stress, the Job Demands-Resources (JDR) Model, and the Conservation of Resources (COR) Theory in understanding the experiences of linemen. Lazarus and Folkman's Transactional Model of Stress supports the study as it shows that linemen are stressed by a high-risk work environment, physical strain, and interpersonal conflicts. Their coping strategies, such as prayer and peer support, align with the model's idea of stress as a result of their appraisal of situations and coping efforts.

However, continued challenges can overwhelm their coping abilities. Furthermore, JDR model, stress arises when job demands exceed available resources. For linemen, hazardous tasks and insufficient resources, such as training and equipment, contribute to stress. The study confirms that adequate resources improve resilience and reduce stress, emphasizing the importance of balancing job demands with resources to prevent burnout. Furthermore, COR theory points out that linemen need to protect and build resources such as social support and faith to manage stress. The study reveals

that linemen rely on these resources, but stress increases when they are depleted, affecting performance and well-being. This underscores the importance of organizational support to help conserve resources and improve coping.

Thus, study confirms the theories' applicability to linemen's challenges, showing that stress, coping mechanisms, and resource availability play a key role in their mental health and job performance. The findings suggest that improving resources (for example, training, and support systems) can enhance coping and reduce stress, which would benefit both the linemen and the work environment.

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